
6. Galactic tracers, by design

IT IS NOT ONLY by good fortune that Gaia is uncovering so much about the structure and kinematics of our Milky Way Galaxy. The design of the scientific instrument, and its operation in orbit, targeted very specific measurement goals, formulated in terms of limiting magnitude, numbers of stars, and their unprecedented astrometric accuracy.

Complementing its astrometric measurements, Gaia was designed, from the start, to include accurate multi-colour multi-epoch photometric measurements that would allow each of its billion or more stars to be characterised, in terms of position in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, metallicity, and reddening.

Put simply, measuring the accurate distances and motions of a billion stars in the Galaxy would be a remarkable achievement in itself. But having a meaningful understanding of each star that had been measured was also enormously desirable.

THE PRIMARY OBJECTIVE of the Gaia mission is to observe the physical characteristics, kinematics and distribution of stars over a large fraction of the volume of our Galaxy, with the goal of achieving a major advance in understanding its dynamics and structure, and consequently its formation and history.

Gaia is making this goal possible by providing, for the first time, a catalogue which is sampling a large and well-defined fraction of the stellar distribution, determining the 3-dimensional positions and space velocities of every star observed, from which significant astrophysical conclusions can be drawn for the entire Galaxy.

Hipparcos did this for the solar neighbourhood. Gaia targets this for a large fraction of the Galaxy.

THE MOST CONSPICUOUS component of the Milky Way is its flat disk, which contains some hundred billion stars of all types and ages orbiting the Galactic centre. The Sun is located about 8.5 kpc from the centre. The disk displays spiral structure, and also contains interstellar material, mainly atomic and molecular hydrogen, and a significant amount of dust.

The inner kpc of the disk also contains the bulge, which is less flattened, may contain a bar, and consists mostly of fairly old stars. At its centre lies a supermassive black hole of about 3 million solar masses.

The disk and bulge are surrounded by a halo of about 10^9 old and metal-poor stars, as well as around 140 globular clusters, and a small number of satellite dwarf galaxies. The entire system is embedded in a massive halo of dark material of unknown composition and poorly known spatial distribution.

The distributions of stars in the Galaxy are linked through gravitational forces, and through the star formation rate as a function of position and time. The initial distributions are modified, perhaps substantially, by small and large scale dynamical processes: these include instabilities which transport angular momentum (bars and warps), and mergers.

UNDERSTANDING OUR GALAXY requires the accurate measurement of distances and space motions for large and unbiased samples of stars of different mass, age, metallicity, and evolutionary stage. The huge number of stars, impressive accuracy, and faint limiting magnitude of Gaia is able to quantify our understanding of the structure and motions within the bulge, the spiral arms, the disk and the outer halo, and is revolutionising dynamical studies of our Galaxy.

A summary of the main Galaxy components and sub-populations is given in the accompanying table, together with the required astrometric accuracies and limiting magnitudes. Compiled by Gilmore & Høg (1995), this was further described in a technical study note by Erik Høg (SAG–CUO–070, 1999), and appeared both in the Gaia Concept & Technology Study Report (ESA–SCI(2000)4, July 2000), and in Perryman et al. (2001).

The idea is that for each sub-population, and its representative kinematic tracers of known absolute magnitude and estimated distance and reddening, we can estimate the corresponding range of V magnitudes, and required astrometric accuracy, over which the populations must be sampled.

(1) Tracer (d = dwarf; g = giant)	(2) M_V mag	(3) ℓ deg	(4) b deg	(5) d kpc	(6) A_V mag	(7) V_1 mag	(8) V_2 mag	(9) ϵ_T km/s	(10) σ_{μ_1} $\mu\text{s/yr}$	(11) σ'_{μ_1} –	(12) σ'_{π_1} –
Bulge:											
• gM	–1	0	< 20	8	2–10	15	20	100	10	0.01	0.10
• horizontal branch	+0.5	0	< 20	8	2–10	17	20	100	20	0.01	0.20
• main-sequence turnoff	+4.5	1	–4	8	0–2	19	21	100	60	0.02	0.6
Spiral arms:											
• Cepheids	–4	all	< 10	10	3–7	14	18	7	5	0.03	0.06
• B–M supergiants	–5	all	< 10	10	3–7	13	17	7	4	0.03	0.05
• Perseus arm (B)	–2	140	< 10	2	2–6	12	16	10	3	0.01	0.01
Thin disk:											
• gK	–1	0	< 15	8	1–5	14	18	40	6	0.01	0.06
• gK	–1	180	< 15	10	1–5	15	19	10	8	0.04	0.10
Disk warp: (gM)	–1	all	< 20	10	1–5	15	19	10	8	0.04	0.10
Disk asymmetry: (gM)	–1	all	< 20	20	1–5	16	20	10	15	0.14	0.4
Thick disk:											
• Miras, gK	–1	0	< 30	8	2	15	19	50	10	0.01	0.10
• horizontal branch	+0.5	0	< 30	8	2	15	19	50	20	0.02	0.20
• Miras, gK	–1	180	< 30	20	2	15	21	30	25	0.08	0.65
• horizontal branch	+0.5	180	< 30	20	2	15	19	30	60	0.20	1.5
Halo:											
• gG	–1	all	< 20	8	2–3	13	21	100	10	0.01	0.10
• horizontal branch	+0.5	all	> 20	30	0	13	21	100	35	0.05	1.4
Gravity (K_Z relation):											
• dK	+7–8	all	all	2	0	12	20	20	60	0.01	0.16
• dF8–dG2	+5–6	all	all	2	0	12	20	20	20	0.01	0.05
Globular clusters: (gK)											
• internal kinematics (gK)	+1	all	all	50	0	12	21	100	10	0.01	0.10
Satellite orbits: (gM)	–1	all	all	100	0	13	20	100	60	0.3	8

IN THIS TABLE, Column 1 lists the various Galaxy populations, and their target ‘tracers’, which can be used to characterise both their distribution in space and their kinematics. These tracers include specific stellar types (e.g. Cepheid, RR Lyrae, or Mira variables), and specific spectral types (here B, F, G, K and M) and luminosity classes (d = dwarf; g = giant). Horizontal branch stars may refer to RR Lyrae, red horizontal branch, or clump giants, as appropriate.

For globular clusters, the cluster itself is used as tracer, with the proper motion referring to the mean of many stars. Globular cluster kinematics refers to the internal kinematics of globular clusters of our Galaxy.

Columns 2–8 list the corresponding photometric data: Column 2 is the absolute visual magnitude of a typical tracer star; Columns 3–4 give the typical Galactic coordinates for that tracers; Column 5 is the typical distance (or upper limit) for each tracer; Column 6 gives the typical visual extinction along the line of sight (for low latitudes the extinction in a Galactic window is given); Columns 7–8 then give the resulting typical range of apparent visual magnitudes over which the chosen tracer can be expected to appear in the Gaia survey.

Columns 9–12 list the relevant astrometric parameters: Column 9 gives the expected velocity dispersion for tracer stars of the sub-population, in the proper motion direction; Column 10 gives the expected Gaia proper motion standard error for a single star at the given representative magnitude; Column 11 gives the expected relative proper motion error; Column 12 gives the expected relative error on Gaia astrometric distances at the representative magnitudes.

LOOKING DOWN Columns 7–8, i.e. at the range of apparent visual magnitudes over which the chosen tracer can be expected to appear, we can see that an astrometric survey probing these different populations and tracers must reach at least down to $V = 14 - 15$ mag, and preferably as faint as $V = 20 - 21$ mag, to reach those specific population representatives. In short, the faint magnitude limit of Gaia, of around 20–21 mag, is essential for probing the different Galaxy populations.

In terms of target astrometric accuracies, Column 11 demonstrates that the proper motions for stars of all listed sub-populations can indeed be measured by Gaia with a significant, and often a superb, precision.